

ESCAPE

ESCAPE (European Science Cluster of Astronomy & Particle physics ESFRI research infrastructures) is a project funded in the European Community research program H2020 to set up a cluster of ESFRI (European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures) facilities for astronomy, astroparticle and particle physics with the purpose of addressing the challenges emerging through the modern multi-disciplinary data driven science. This cluster aims to state a functional connection between the interested ESFRI projects and the EOSC (European Open Science Cloud) providing tools and solutions according to FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) principles.

ESAP

One of the main goal of ESCAPE is the building of ESAP (ESFRI Science Analysis Platform), a flexible and expandable science platform for the analysis of open access data available through the EOSC environment. ESAP will allow EOSC researchers to identify and stage existing data collections for analysis, share data, share and run scientific workflows.

HPC and HTC Integration

For many ESFRIs and Research Infrastructures, the data scales involved require significant computational resources (storage and compute) to support processing and analysis. The EOSC-ESFRI science platform therefore must implement appropriate interfaces to an underlying HPC (High Performance Computing) or HTC (High Throughput Computing) infrastructure to take advantage of it. ESAP aims to provide users the ability to access data and to deploy user-initiated processing and analysis tasks on HTC and HPC infrastructures both in batch mode and maintaining interactivity. Responsiveness in the analysis system will be a challenge.

This poster describes the analysis done to identify the main requirements in terms of authentication and authorization policies, data management, computation resources management and software run to enable the ESAP to integrate HPC and HTC computation resources.

General Use Case: scenarios

First scenario: the data analysis performs in computing resources associated to the data lake, in the same infrastructure.

Second scenario: the data analysis performs in computing resources not associated to the data lake, i.e. in a computing center different from which hosting the data lake.

In both scenarios a software able to manage data and software deployment access and upload in the computation infrastructure is needed. Investigation of different solutions is in progress evaluating Jupyter to data lake (Rucio) implementations, Dirac or other schedulers (Rosetta).

Authentication & Authorization

In Astronomy and Astrophysics fields data are public in the most cases, sometimes after a relatively short embargo period. For this reason authentication (to know who is the user) and authorization (to give access to specific quantified resources, both storage and computation) seems to be not an issue.

This is not true in case of access and use of HPC and HTC infrastructures because they generally have usage policies, sometimes applied also to assess billing policies. So the computation infrastructures need to identify who is connecting and how to apply access and usage policies. For this reason authentication and authorization issues must be taken into account and to be faced at two levels:

- ESFRI Science Analysis Platform level (sometimes can be optional)
- Data and Computing Center level (mandatory)

Data Management

To analyze data in an computation infrastructure (HPC or HTC), they must be staged in a storage area associated to and accessible by the infrastructure.

Through ESAP the user can search and select data (See P1-59).

In the environment of the ESCAPE project, a prototype of an open access data lake for the ESCAPE community has been set up: the ESCAPE Data Infrastructure for Open Science (DIOS), also called data lake. Data downloaded from a public web server can be transferred into the data lake and their path is exposed to users, using the RUCIO data management service.

The integration of HPC and HTC infrastructures in ESAP requires to exploit these features: data selected through ESAP must be staged in the DIOS and, when needed for analysis, transferred in a target computing center exploiting RUCIO capabilities.

Workflow Management

The user who wants to analyze data exploiting an HPC or HTC infrastructure has the need to deploy analysis software in the target infrastructure where data must be available. To satisfy the different scenarios depicted above a task description is needed. It should contain: the user identity and rights of access to data and to software; the data location and, if needed, the transfer information (protocols and tools); the analysis software identifier, the location and, if needed, the transfer information. The environment must be suitably configured in case not self-contained software. Containers, for example, could be used to simplify this task.